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Development of a novel hand flame manikin facility to estimate firefighters' burn injuries

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Introduction

Firefighters are exposed to a variety of hazards while on the job. Burns the typical – firefighting occupational injury are common and often disfiguring as well as extremely painful [1]. Firefighting PPE is designed to provide protection from occupational hazards such as high-temperatures, flames, and combusting objects. Because of its importance PPE performance is evaluated both in terms of its material and in terms of whole garment. A static, upright and human-sized manikin is used for testing the performance of personal protective ensembles. However, most of these manikins do not have heat flux sensors on the hands so that gloves cannot be tested, despite the fact that the hands/wrists are one of the most common burn injury regions [2-3]. These manikins also have the disadvantage of not reflecting changes in performance due to posture or movement. For these very reasons we developed an advanced hand flame manikin facility prototype for measuring the thermal protective performance of whole gloves. We especially made the flame hand manikin system capable of height and angle adjustments and rotatable for reflecting the dynamic nature of firefighting activities. We also have conducted a pilot test to verify the performance of the newly-developed facility.

System Overview

The hand flame manikin facility consisted of a flame exposure chamber, a burner system, and a flame hand manikin system (Figure 1).

Flame exposure chamber and burner system

The interior dimensions of the chamber that we developed were W 2,550 × D 2,850 × H 2,600 mm. It was designed exclusively for evaluating small-sized PPE such as gloves and is thus easy to handle.

The interior of the chamber was made from 25T-refractory plaster board and its exterior was made from 50T SUS 304 sandwich panel and fitted with a forced air exhaust system and a safety system which includes two fire sprinklers with high-temperature flame detectors, a propane gas circuit breaker, emergency stops, eight gas solenoid valves for each burners, etc. We also installed an elaborate misting device with a compressor in the chamber to simulate humid firefighting situations. Additionally the chamber was equipped with an observation window (600 square mm, 5T), a sealed fire-proof door and a video monitoring system. The burner system used propane gas as a fuel to meet the requirements of ISO 9162 (2013). Four pairs of two (a total of eight) propane gas torches were configured to produce a thermal exposure intensity averaging 84 kW/m² across the surface of the hand as stipulated by ISO 13506-1 (2017) and ASTM F1930 (2017). And each burner can be adjusted up to 180°.

Flame hand manikin system

The hand manikin system consisted of a stand-alone life-sized right hand with a rotating plate and a vertical height adjustable stand mounted in the flame exposure chamber. A Large-size glove was fitted for the hand flame manikin. The hand flame manikin was fitted with eleven heat flux sensors (0.1 s per measurement) on the stainless steel surface. Two of these were located on the ventral surface (palm), two on the dorsal surface (back) of the hand and another four on the anterior and posterior regions of the wrist. Three additional sensors were located on the ventral surface of the index and middle finger, and the medial side of the thumb. And the hand manikin can be rotated 360° in 10 s and its height adjusted from 1,000 to 1,600 mm according to test protocols.

Pilot test results and conclusions

A pilot test was performed to evaluate the performance of the prototype hand flame manikin facility. This test consisted of twelve trials focusing on torch angles (45° and 90°), the movement of the manikin (standstill and 360° rotation/10 s), and glove conditions (bare hand, drying gloves, and wet gloves) ($2 \times 2 \times 3 = 12$). The experimental gloves were flame-resistant model that is currently used by

Figure 1. Flame hand manikin (left), flame exposure chamber (middle), and structure of torches (right).

firefighters in Seoul, Korea. The results of a 10-s flame exposure showed that the hand flame manikin facility produced a mean value of 84 kW/m^2 , but the density of heat flux among the 11 sensors showed deviation over 15%. The great deviation is the foremost consideration for improving the newly-developed facility. Angles of torches had significant influences on the heat flux showing that a diagonal flame from below (45°-angle) induced greater heat flux and larger flame size than a horizontal flame (90°-angle). There were no significant differences in the average values of heat flux density during the 10-s flame exposure between the static and rotating conditions, and between the dry and wet glove conditions, but the standard deviation in the heat flux density under the rotating conditions tended to be relatively large. Interestingly, materials of dry gloves were damaged, showing shrinkage and combustion, whereas wet gloves largely maintained their exterior form. These results demonstrate that the protective performance of gloves can be altered by variables outside the existing test methods, such as the posture, movement and the wetness of the PPE during firefighting. Such variables could be the driving force behind the development of the unique firefighting gloves more suitable for work in the field. But new test method reflecting such external variables should also be developed. While our newly-developed facility is expected to be useful, the improvement of the above-mentioned problem should take precedence in order to obtain stable and valid results.

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